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Research Article

**CLINICAL FEATURES OF PATIENT WITH UREMIC
PRURITUS ENDURING HEMODIALYSIS****¹Dr Hira Iqbal, ²Dr Shabnam Rustamani, ³Dr Reham Baig**¹Quaid-e-Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur²Lecturer in Department of Pathology, Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences
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Dental College, Dina Nath**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:****Aim:** To identify the different characteristics of uremic pruritus in patients undergoing hemodialysis.**Study design:** A case series**Study location and duration:** This study was conducted at the Department of Nephrology and Dermatology of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from February 2019 to February 2020.**Patients and Methods:** Fifty patients with end-stage renal disease undergoing hemodialysis were studied. Characteristics of the pruritus such as duration, severity, occurrence, appearance, distribution, area of maximum intensity; effects on and mood have been documented. Effects of dry skin, heat, sweating, rest, clothing, fatigue, dialysis, cold, moisturizing, medications, and itching have been analyzed.**Results:** Pruritus seen in 90% daily, 22% weekly, 14% monthly, and incurable in 8%. The areas of maximum intensity are 66% of the legs and 34% of the back. Dry skin and cold environment exacerbated while rest and hot environment a meliorated pruritus. 76% had sleep problems 34% became agitated, while 18% became depressed patients with pruritus did not differ from those without it with regard to laboratory parameter or use of medication.**Conclusion:** This study gives us a comprehensive characterization of uremic pruritus, which may be a useful clue for treating nephrologists and dermatologists.**Key words:** Uremic Pruritus, Hemodialysis, Chronic renal failure, End stage renal disease.**Corresponding author:****Dr Hira Iqbal,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Chronic renal failure (CRF) is a major medical problem worldwide. The incidence and prevalence is steadily increasing. Its main cause is diabetes mellitus, followed by chronic glomerulonephritis, hypertension, polycystic kidney disease, obstructive uropathy, and nephrotoxic drugs. Itching is one of the most common symptoms in uremic patients, especially those undergoing hemodialysis¹. Other common symptoms are nausea, shortness of breath, fatigue, etc. The pathogenesis of uremic pruritus is unclear and may be due to several factors². Dialysis is an important trigger of pruritus. A likely cause is the slowly settling or accumulating uncertain pruritus. Most patients with chronic renal failure have elevated parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels, which can cause mast cells to proliferate in the skin, leading to the release of histamine, which itself causes itching³. Hypophosphatemia, abnormal patterns of continuous innervation and elevated vitamin A levels have been associated with uremic pruritus. Xerosis is also a contributing factor to itching. Pruritus is a common problem in hemodialysis patients⁴. Extensive clinical data is needed to design an effective treatment strategy for uremic pruritus, and data on its clinical characteristics are sparse, especially in our own population⁵. Our study was designed to provide comprehensive data on the clinical characteristics of uremic pruritus so that it could provide useful guidance to treating nephrologists and dermatologists⁶.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This study was conducted at the Department of Nephrology and Dermatology of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from February 2019 to February 2020. It was conducted for 6 months, from January to June 2008. It was a series of cases. The study included 50 patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) who were undergoing maintenance hemodialysis. Patients of both sexes and all age groups with CRF pruritus caused by an accessory

disease or patients with chronic renal failure taking anti-pruritus medications were excluded from the study. Patients with CRF who met the inclusion / exclusion criteria were interviewed after obtaining their consent. Associated with pruritus and various laboratory parameters such as mean blood urea and creatinine values before dialysis. Uric acid, calcium, phosphorus, hematocrit, alkaline phosphate, bilirubin, PTH and total heparin dose obtained in a single dialysis were recorded. The severity of pruritus was assessed as mild (relief from itching by rubbing), moderate (relief by scratching), severe (itching with erosions) and incurable (irresistible urge to scratch leading to sleep disturbance). The incidence of pruritus, demographic characteristics of the study group, demographic characteristics of patients with uremic pruritus, duration of pruritus, appearance of pruritus after starting dialysis, nature, duration, intensity, area of maximum severity, effect on sleep, mood, distribution of pruritus was noted. The appearance of pruritus has been associated with the regular use of any medications, such as calcium channel blockers, alpha or beta blockers, angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors, aspirin, nitrates or a combination of these drugs. Data were obtained from patients through personal interviews and a preliminary proforma plan was used to record all relevant information. Descriptive statistics such as duration, relative frequency, aggravating / mitigating factors, intensity and location were calculated to represent the data.

RESULT:

Periods of time on dialectic therapy ranged from 2 months to 5 years. All these patients underwent dialysis for a period of 4 hours twice weekly only 6% patients underwent three times in week due to overload of patients. The main dialyzer used was cellulose diacetate (80% of them were 150E (1.5m²) and the rest 103E (1.3m²). Standard purified water was used.

Table 1: Characteristics of uremic pruritus

	Frequency	%age
Duration of pruritus		
More than 1 year	4	8.0
More than 2 years	6	12.0
More than 3 years	40	80.0
Occurrence of pruritus		
Daily	45	90.0
Weekly	3	6.0
Monthly	2	4.0
Appearance of pruritus		
2-3 months after start of dialysis	41	82
2 years of start of dialysis	17	34.0

Intensity of pruritus		
Mild	25	50.0
Moderate	14	28.0
Severe	7	14.0
Intractable	4	8.0
Characteristics of pruritus		
Intermittent	31	62.0
Continuous	9	18.0
Nocturnal exacerbation	10	20.0
Distribution of pruritus		
Symmetrical	20	40.0
Asymmetrical	30	60.0
Areas of maximum intensity		
Legs	33	66.0
Back	17	34.0
Effect of pruritus on mood		
Agitated	17	34.0
Depressed	9	18.0
Effect of pruritus on sleep		
Difficulty in falling to sleeps	29	58.0
Awakened by pruritus	9	18

In our study the pruritus was present in 27 (54%) cases. Out of these 22 (44%) were male while 28 (56%) were female. The average age of patients with pruritus was 51 years while that of without pruritus was 43%. Pruritus was more common in those patients, who were on maintenance hemodialysis for more than 3 years as compare to one and two years of duration. The majority of the patients 25 (50%) complained of mild degree of pruritus. The pruritus distributed asymmetrically in most of the cases 30 (60%). During rest pruritus have no effect in 40% cases while it is a meliorating in 34% cases. During dialysis. Majority of the patients, 35 (70%) have no pruritic effect, while in 9 (18%) cases it is exacerbating. After dialysis it is exacerbating in most cases 29 (58%) in our study. During cold pruritus exacerbating in 30 (60%) cases while applying oil to skin pruritus 100% is ameliorating. The results are summarized in Tables 1-2.

Table 2: Characteristics of uremic pruritus aggravating and ameliorating factors

Factors	No effect	Ameliorating	Exacerbating
Dry skin	18 (36%)	-	32 (64%)
Heat	27 (54%)	20 (40%)	3 (6%)
Rest	20 (40%)	17 (34%)	13 (26%)
Sweating	27 (54%)	14 (28%)	9 (18%)
Clothing	36 (72%)	7 (14%)	7 (14%)
Tiredness	46 (92%)	3 (6%)	1 (2%)
During dialysis	35 (70%)	6 (12%)	9 (18%)
Before dialysis	26 (52%)	20 (40%)	4 (8%)
Cold	17 (34%)	3 (6%)	30 (60%)
After dialysis	15 (30%)	6 (12%)	29 (58%)
Medication	50 (100%)	-	-
Laboratory parameters	50 (100%)	-	-
Applying oil to skin	-	50 (100%)	-

DISCUSSION:

Uremic pruritus is one of the most common symptoms in patients with chronic renal failure. Uremic pruritus was observed in 54% of patients in our study. Pruritus appeared within 2-3 months of starting dialysis in 41 (82%) cases in our study⁷. Gilcrest and Jackic reported the onset of pruritus soon after dialysis in 25% and 19% of patients, respectively. Robertson in his review stated that the pruritus appeared about 6-8 months after starting dialysis⁸. On the other hand, a study by Hirosighe showed that optimal dialysis improves uremic pruritus, so our data and other studies suggest that dialysis may cause itching. The slight difference in the occurrence of itching after dialysis may be related to the type of dialysate used⁹. Varying rates of pruritus incidence are 22%, 37.9%, 40.8%, 40-70% compared to 54% in our study, so the incidence of uremic pruritus is variable, but on average it may be about 40% of patients. The duration of the pruritus was usually extended¹⁰. 40 (80%) patients had pruritus for more than three years. Although long-lasting, it was not necessarily consistent with the duration of dialysis and was free from it at the time of our study. The Gilcrest 7 study led to the same conclusion. In contrast, Stahle and Backdahl concluded that uremic pruritus tends to persist during dialysis¹¹. These different conclusions may be due to differences in sample size and length of observations. Pruritus was symmetrical in 20 (40%) of the patients in our study¹². It covers the entire body but is more localized in the legs 33 (66%). This is similar to the result obtained by Zucker who indicated the back (70%) and the abdomen (46%) as the most frequently affected area¹³. Due to its long duration, frequency and severity, uremic pruritus is very troublesome for some symptoms and may be life-threatening. This was related to some of the patients in our study, 17 (34%) patients were agitated and 9 (18%) became depressed as a result of itching. In 24 (48%) patients, pruritus did not affect their mood¹⁴. Zucker et al. Reported an incidence of 36%, 8% and 52%, respectively, in patients who were agitated and depressed with no effect. Itching appeared daily in the majority of our 45 patients (90%) and was intermittent and not evenly distributed throughout the day. In our study, it was more frequent and more intense at night¹⁵. This was also noticed by Balaskas 16, which can be attributed to the lack of activity typical of this part of the day. The severity of pruritus in our study was mild in 25 (50%), moderate in 14 (28%), and severe in 7 (14%). Balaskas 17 reported pruritus as mild in 43% of patients, moderate in 41% and severe in 14% of patients undergoing hemodialysis¹⁶.

CONCLUSION:

From this study, it appears that uremic pruritus occurred in nearly half of the patients with CRF receiving hemodialysis. Hemodialysis was a common trigger, and itching usually started within 3 months of starting it. Most of the pruritus was mild, but a third of the patients were agitated or depressed as a result of itching. It was common every day and was intermittent. Half of the patients slept with this problem. This test can provide useful guidance for nephrologists and dermatologists. This study also gives us a comprehensive characterization of uremic pruritus in our own population.

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